

The *villa rustica* of Deutschkreutz

Integrated archaeological prospection of one of the largest Roman *villae* in Austria

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Abstract—The Roman *villa rustica* in the so-called “Steinmühläcker” in Deutschkreutz, Austria, has been subject of an integrated archaeological prospection survey conducted in 2009 using magnetics and ground penetrating radar (GPR). The building complex turned out to be one of the largest in Austria, and at least three different building phases can be distinguished. The geophysical data have been interpreted within a GIS-environment and 3D-reconstruction models have been created using Google Sketchup.

Keywords—Magnetics; GPR; Roman villa; GIS-based interpretation; 3D-reconstruction

I. INTRODUCTION

After the discovery of a small Roman mosaic floor in a field in Deutschkreutz, Austria, the Austrian Archaeological Institute has carried out archaeological excavations in the years 1988 to 1991 [1 – 4]. These excavations have been restricted to a relatively small area of a large *villa* complex, but brought forward numerous very interesting features and finds. In 2009 a geophysical archaeological prospection survey has been conducted using magnetics and GPR. This survey was a joined project of Archeo Prospections® (ZAMG) and the Institute of Archaeology of the University of Graz.

During the archaeological prospection survey an area of some 17,500 m² and approximately 12,900 m² were covered with magnetics, respectively with GPR. The surveyed area included at least 11 buildings – houses, courts and agricultural buildings located north of a road. Altogether, the *villa* complex covers an area of about 8,000 m² and has to be considered to be amongst the largest Roman *villae* known in Austria.

II. GEOPHYSICAL ARCHAEOLOGICAL SURVEY

A. Magnetic survey

The magnetic survey was carried out using a Foerster Fluxgate FEREX STD magnetometer system consisting of four gradiometer probes with a cross-line sensor-spacing of 0.5 m.

The data have been resampled onto a regular grid of 0.1 x 0.1 m. Using APMag – an in-house developed software by Archeo Prospections® – greyscale images using different dynamic ranges between -32 to -2 and +3 to +48 nanotesla (nT) were generated (fig. 1). These images have subsequently been georeferenced using six fix-points for which global coordinates were determined using a differential GPS instrument. The georeferenced data images were then imported into ArcGIS 9.3, permitting advanced archaeological interpretation and integration of additional information, such as earlier excavation maps, aerial photographs and other spatial data.

Fig. 1: Magnetogram of the geophysical survey of the Roman *villa* of Deutschkreutz, Austria. Greyscale dynamics: -8 nT (black) to +12 nT (white) in 254 steps.

B. Ground Penetrating Radar survey

For the GPR survey a Sensors & Software Noggin Plus and a PulseEKKOPro georadar system each equipped with a 500 MHz antenna has been used. The line spacing was 0.5 m and the in-line trace spacing 0.05 m.

Before the calculation of the absolute amplitude of a determined depth slice, the GPR measurement signals have been preprocessed. Digital image processing algorithms have been used in order to enhance the visualization of the greyscale images. Horizontal depth slices of 0.1 to 0.5 m vertical distance have been produced out of the datablocks in form of digital B/W-images. Out of those images the depth areas which contained the most information of archaeologically relevant structures have been selected and produced (fig. 2). All images have been georeferenced using the GPS fix-points and imported into ArcGIS for further interpretation.

Fig. 2: Depth-slice 0.5 to 1.6 m of the GPR survey of the Roman villa of Deutschkreutz, Austria.

III. ARCHAEOLOGICAL ANALYSIS

The prospection data show a large complex consisting of several wings and annexes and some adjoining buildings, more or less connected to each other. The main orientation of the building complex is NW-SE, with some deviations.

As shown in figure 3, in the NW of the survey area a structure has been detected (marked with **A** in the interpretation map), which appears as an aisled house of possible younger age compared to the main parts of the villa, due to its deviating orientation and the shallower depth of the associated structures. The same dating may apply to building **B** to the NE of the main building of the villa. This structure could be interpreted to have consisted of a large kiln used to dry crop.

Building **C** is situated in the western part of the complex and is the largest structure of all. The size of the building measures approximately 35 by 24 m and it shows adjoining buildings at its eastern and western sides. The interior of building **C** contains detailed subdivisions and features 19 rooms. In the centre of the building a corridor can be seen, surrounded by all other rooms.

Within the extent of this main building the greater part of the archaeological excavation took place. An area covering 53 by 11.5 m has been excavated and documented archaeologically. A number of rooms could be identified and several buildings phases detected. The excavation area included the location where the initially found floor mosaic had been discovered.

Building **C** seems to be the living quarters of the villa. Similar buildings with a central corridor are known from nearby Roman villas in Hungary.

Fig. 3: Complete archaeological interpretation of the geophysical prospection data of the Roman villa of Deutschkreutz, Austria.

Structure **D** comprises one of the two courts found in the villa. In the magnetogram there is a large number of thermoremanent features visible, which may be caused by the remains of bricks or roof tiles.

Building **E** in the eastern part of the complex is an elongated rectangular structure measuring 40.5 by 13 m. Its interior is divided in two rooms, of which the larger one is situated in the North. This larger room features rows of 8 column bases each. The building seems to have been the main storage room (*horreum*) of the complex.

The structure labeled **F** is the main corridor of the complex, running in EW direction and connecting several parts of the villa. Two quadratic rooms may have been tower-like annexes.

Building **G** in the SE area of the complex is partly unprospected due to a modern road overlaying it. Based on the known layout of the complex this building may have been the *villa's* bath.

To the East of the bath there is another large building labeled **H**. This structure seems to have been another living quarter, but may have been demolished during a modification phase. The excavation covered a small area of this building and the finds indicate that it possibly had been occupied by servants.

Directly east to the building **H** another court **I** is located, bordering to the road **L** in the south. East of this smaller court yard there are two additional buildings (**J** and **K**), which may have been agriculturally used structures of unknown function.

Fig. 4: 3D-reconstruction of structures **C**, **D**, **E** and **F** of the Roman *villa* of Deutschkreutz, Austria, using *Google Sketchup* software.

IV. CONCLUSION

The Roman *villa* of Deutschkreutz is one of the largest *villa* complexes of Austria and has possibly been one of the most impressive buildings of its kind. The complex shows at least three, maybe four building phases according to the results of the excavation and the directions and depths of the detectable archaeological structures in the geophysical data. The construction of buildings **C** to **I** can be dated to the first part of

the 4th century AD due to the finds of the excavations. A phase of remodeling of these buildings, which also has been dated by the excavations to the second half of the 4th century, has been proven.

The rich grave 1 of the cemetery corresponding to the *villa* provides some hints about a possible earlier phase, because its finds have been dated to the end of the 2nd century AD. Buildings **A**, **B**, **J** and **K** show different orientations than the other buildings and may possibly date to a younger phase, because of the shallower depth-slices in which they appear.

The layout of this *villa* as a large and interconnected complex is rather untypical and not comparable to any other of the well-known *villa* types of the Roman Empire. No similar complex could be found in the literature.

The location in the vicinity of the amber road, approximately 10 kilometres south of the Roman town of Scarbantia (Sopron, Hungary) may be an indicator of an important supply position of the *villa* in the hinterland of a *municipium*. The land tenure can only be guessed so far. It could either have been a state-run farm owned by the emperor himself and managed by a procurator, or by a private leaseholder. Alternatively it could have been private property altogether, owned by an individual who was able to increase the income out of the *villa* sufficiently to erect the extensive and magnificent complex mapped by the archaeological prospection survey.

REFERENCES

- [1] P. Scherrer, "Notgrabung einer römischen Villa in Deutschkreutz", *Pro Austria Romana* 38, 1988, Heft 6/7, pp. 13-16.
- [2] P. Scherrer, "Deutschkreutz – römische Villa", *Jahreshefte des Österr. Archäolog. Instituts*, 59, 1989, pp. 15-17.
- [3] P. Scherrer, "Deutschkreutz – römische Villa", *Jahreshefte des Österr. Archäolog. Instituts*, 60, 1990, pp. 48-50.
- [4] P. Scherrer, "Deutschkreutz – römische Villa", *Jahreshefte des Österr. Archäolog. Instituts*, 61, 1991, pp. 31-33.
- [5] F. Mauthner, *Römerzeitliche Gutshöfe in Westpannonien*. Unpublished diploma thesis, University of Graz, 2010.